

Information as a Conserved Quantity? Part 3

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In Part 2, we argued that a single Newtonian elastic collision already contains the notion of probability and information. In particular, one may suggest that $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j)$ for any $e_i + e_j = e_1 + e_2$. In other words, there is equal probability to have any outcome pair e_i, e_j that conserves energy. This is an idealized case, but it suggests that there is a certain fixed amount of information present in a single collision and the rest lost, we argue. We then suggested in Part 2 that this single collision be extended to the case of many such collisions in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. Next, we considered the situation of multiple probabilities (two in particular) in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein scenarios. The main idea is that there exists a quantity, (a function of $p(e_i)$) which is called information and is conserved. This means that changing $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ leads to first order terms in $dp(e_i)$ which must vanish when summed. In Part 2, we specifically considered the information science definition of information, namely $\ln(\text{probability})$.

Here we try to generalize the idea of conserved information, even if it means going beyond the definition of information science as in the Tsallis case. Information may be generalized and there may be multiple probabilities in a problem, but information should be conserved. This means that the first order term in $dp(e_i)$ must vanish when summed over i , but given the two usual constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E/N$ (or similar constraints), the differentials of these must be respected when considering the differential term of information. This leads to the usual association of differential terms of information with differential terms of these two constraints (or similar constraints) as a possible math solution. This approach accounts for the MB, FD, BE and Tsallis scenarios, but not for the Kaniadakis one.

Intrinsic Information in a Problem

We argued in Part 2, that even a single Newtonian elastic two body collision seems to contain probability (i.e. information). In particular, if an e_1 and e_2 energy particle collide, the resulting pair must have e_i, e_j with $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$. The question is: Which pair e_i, e_j emerges? We argue that even in Newtonian mechanics one would usually not have enough physical information to answer this question and the simplest approach is assume that all e_i, e_j pairs which sum to $e_1 + e_2$ have the same product probability:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_1)p(e_2), e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \rightarrow p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ (Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution)} \quad ((1))$$

Physically, matters are not always as simple as ((1)) as in the Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) cases discussed in Part 2. The point we wish to make is that ((1)) represents a loss of some information (linked with the notion of probability). We argue that a statistical system may be linked a priori with a certain amount of physical information. In Part 2, we tried to associate this concept of information with the information science definition:

$\ln(\text{probability}) = \text{information} \quad ((2))$

In the FD and BE cases, we tried to argue that one may have multiple probabilities and hence multiple information terms, but still adhere to ((2)). Here we suggest that information may in fact be generalized from the definition ((2)). First, however, we wish to consider the relationship between information and constraints of conserved quantities in a problem.

Constraints of Conserved Quantities in a Problem

In Part 2, we argued that given that total energy is written in terms of an average:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) = E/N \quad ((3))$$

one may define a quantity called information $h(p(e_i))$. At this point h is not automatically equivalent to the \ln function as in the informational science case. As seen in Part 1, one may have multiple probabilities in a problem such as in the FD or BE case. In those cases, secondary probabilities are linear functions of $p(e_i)$. One may introduce an information function based on the physics/interactions in a problem through:

$$\text{Sum over } j \text{ } P_j(p(e_i)) \text{ } h_j (P_j(p(e_i)) \quad ((4))$$

Here the average of information is used as in ((3)), but ((4)) should represent an overall total information which is conserved, meaning the differential of ((4)) must be 0.

We first start with the simple case of $j=1$ and $P_j=1$ so that information is:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) h(p(e_i)) \text{ and } d \text{ information} = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } h(p(e_i)) dp(e_i) + p(e_i) dh/dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((5))$$

A physical problem usually has conserved quantities such as ((3)) and $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) = 1$. The differentials of these are also 0. In the simplest scenario, one might try to force terms of ((5)) to match the differentials of these two constraints. Physically, this is justified for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases by examining reaction balance. In these cases, one needs to consider the statistical physics associated with a reaction. Otherwise it is not clear how to link ((5)) to the differentials of the constraints. In such a case, one may set:

$$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ and } p(e_i) dh(p(e_i))/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad ((6)) \text{ to obtain } p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$$

In previous notes, we tended to associate $h(p(e_i))$ a priori with energy, but we argue that in general, it represents information. In the simple MB case, it immediately maps to $-e_i/T$, but not in the more complicated FD and BE cases as shown explicitly in Part 2.

We note that in the simple case of ((6)), $h(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i))$, i.e. the \ln function emerges directly from the "chosen" link between the differential of information and the differentials of the two conserved constraints.

We next ask whether one may obtain an information expression which does make use $\ln(p(e_i))$.

The Tsallis Case

The above recipe suggests that one define an information function $h(p(e_i))$, take its average with respect to a probability used to create average e_i , it seems, and then suggest that the differential of $\sum_i P(p(e_i)) h(p(e_i)) e_i$ is 0. Here again we only consider one independent probability $P(p(e_i))$ which depends on $p(e_i)$. Then:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \sum_i P(p(e_i)) e_i = \text{number} \quad ((7)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$dP(p(e_i)) h(p(e_i)) + P(p(e_i)) dh/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((8))$$

Again, one may try to map ((8)) to the differentials of ((7)). The first differential is $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$. Presumably, $dP/dp(e_i)$ is not the inverse of information and so the first term should map to the second constraint in ((7)) and the second term to the first. (Note: This is only a possible math approach, not the only approach allowed. It is in fact a simple solution to the problem.) Then:

$$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{and} \quad P(p(e_i)) dh/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{In the Tsallis case, one has the physical scenario: } P(p(e_i)) = p(e_i)^q \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{This leads to: } h(p(e_i)) = 1/(1-q) \{1 - p(e_i)^q\} \quad ((11))$$

Thus, information does not need to be $\ln(p(e_i))$ or \ln of linear probability in $p(e_i)$ as in the FD and BE cases.

More General Case

If one combines the Tsallis situation with that of the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein (i.e. multiple probabilities), then one might expect an information expression of the form:

$$\sum_j P_j(p(e_i)) h_j(p(e_i)) \quad ((12))$$

If the differential of this quantity is to match constraints $\sum_i p(e_i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i P_1(p(e_i)) = \text{constant}$, for example. P_2, P_3 etc may then be probabilities (unnormalized) like $(1-p(e_i))$ or $(1+p(e_i))$ as in the FD or BE cases. Only $p(e_i)$ in such a case is used in the average energy constraint in the FD or BE cases.

Do All Cases Conform to the Above Scenario?

We have mapped the differentials of the conserved quantities to the differential of information in a specific manner which is not mathematically general. The above scheme accounts for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac (2 probabilities), Bose-Einstein (2 probabilities) and Tsallis cases, but not for the Kaniadakis case. As a result, information considerations seem to be more complicated than what is described above, but at least there are some simpler cases, we argue.

Conclusion

In Part 2, we considered the definition of information as following from information science, i.e. $\ln(\text{probability})$. Here we argue that one may be more general. We define a function $h(p(e_i))$ as information and argue that its conservation means that: $\sum_i P(p(e_i)) h(p(e_i))$ is conserved. Here $P(p(e_i))$ may be a more general probability than $p(e_i)$ which is used to calculate average e_i , i.e. $\sum_i P(p(e_i)) e_i = \text{constant}$. In the simplest case, $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E/N$. If one considers that information is conserved, one may set the differential of $\sum_i P(p(e_i)) h(p(e_i))$ to 0, but the differentials of the constraints must also be 0. Thus, there must be compatibility between all three conserved differentials (information, energy, and particle number). In this note, we consider a simple mapping approach between the differential of information and the differentials of the energy and particle number constraints which accounts for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac, Bose-Einstein and Tsallis cases, but not for the Kaniadakis case, which seems to be more complicated. We see that information is not always $\ln(\text{probability})$ as in the Tsallis case.